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**Discursive shifts associated with coming out: A corpus-based analysis of news reports
about Ricky Martin**

Heiko Motschenbacher

English Abstract

This study seeks to shed light on the discursive effects of a public sexual identity declaration as they surface in the language used to construct the social actor in question. Subscribing to queer linguistically informed critical discourse studies, it builds on and advances the theoretical discussion of coming out in language and sexuality studies. The investigation analyses a corpus of news reports about Ricky Martin, comparing two sub-corpora, one with

texts published before and another with texts from after Martin's public coming out as a gay man in 2010. A keyword analysis is performed to identify linguistic traces of central discourses manifesting in the two corpora. The quantitative analysis is complemented by an in-depth qualitative analysis of the discursive construction of ethnicity and sexuality in two sample texts. The findings are discussed in the light of discursive shifts between pre- and post-coming-out phases and clashes between coming-out stereotypes and the coming-out experiences of Latino gay men.

Keywords: news coverage; coming out; language and sexuality; corpus linguistics; critical discourse studies; Latino gay men

Short running title: Discursive shifts associated with coming out

Word count: 9,979 (all inclusive); main text: 6,716

Norsk sammendrag

Denne studien søker å belyse de diskursive virkningene av en offentlig seksuell identitetserklæring slik disse kommer til uttrykk i språket som brukes til å konstruere den respektive samfunnsaktøren. Studien følger queer lingvistisk informerte kritiske diskursstudier, og den bygger på og fremmer den teoretiske diskusjonen rundt å komme ut i språk- og seksualitetsstudier. Undersøkelsen analyserer et korpus av nyhetsmedienes tekster om Ricky Martin og sammenligner to delkorporer, én med tekster som ble publisert før, og én med tekster som er datert etter Martins offisielt kom ut som homofil i 2010. Det utføres en nøkkelordanalyse for å identifisere språklige spor av sentrale diskurser som dukker opp i

de to delkorpusene. Den kvantitative analysen er supplert med en inngående kvalitativ analyse av den diskursive konstruksjonen av etnisitet og seksualitet i to eksempeltekster. Resultatene blir diskutert i lys av diskursive forskyvninger mellom før og etter de kommer ut og sammenstøt mellom stereotype representasjoner av coming out og latinamerikanske, homofile menns opplevelser i forbindelse med at de kommer ut.

Nøkkelord: nyhetsdekning; coming out; språk og seksualitet; korpuslingvistikk; kritiske diskurs studier; latinamerikanske homofile menn

INTRODUCTION

Although coming out is widely perceived to be a pivotal moment in the lives of non-heterosexual people, we currently know little about its discursive effects. It is plausible that the way we use language to describe a person changes after their coming out. But is this actually the case, and if so, how does the discursive construction of that person change? This paper sheds light on these questions. This is important for two reasons: to raise awareness about the discursive consequences of coming out and to advance the sociolinguistic discussion of coming out through corpus-based evidence.

No other public coming out has transpired on such a global scale as that of Latino pop star Ricky Martin. The discursive construction of Martin's persona by the media has projected various normativities on him, raising questions such as whether Martin is Puerto Rican enough, Latino enough, US American enough, masculine enough or a good enough singer (Calafell 2007: 87-119; Lugo-Lugo 2012, Negrón-Muntaner 2004: 247-271). Sexual normativities also have been central in this public negotiation (Calafell 2007: 100-111; Lugo-Lugo 2012, Rivera Santana, Vélez Agosto, Benozzo & Colón de la Rosa 2014).

Born as Enrique José Martín Morales in Puerto Rico in 1971, Ricky Martin achieved early fame in the boyband Menudo. Anglicising his stage name, he successfully went solo in 1991. Despite persistent speculation about his sexuality in the international media (see Quiroga 2000: 181-190), Martin came out fairly late in his career, on March 29, 2010. The goal of this study is to investigate how this event changed the way news media linguistically construct Ricky Martin's persona by analysing media coverage before and after the artist came out. It yields evidence of how coming out affects a celebrity's public image, but also reveals mechanisms that are more generally associated with coming out.

COMING OUT AND LATINO GAY MEN

The theoretical approach of this study is informed by queer linguistics (Motschenbacher 2010, 2011, 2014) and its critical stance on sexuality-related discourses. Conceptualising identities as essentialising categories, queer linguistics questions the stability and 'naturalness' of identities as well as the normativities associated with identity categories. From this perspective, identities are both a blessing, because they give social actors greater recognition and political momentum, and a curse, because they tend to create exclusion, marginalisation and stigmatisation.

Although coming out may seem to be a transgressive act, since it is the self-affirming of an identity that is widely perceived as non-normative, there are limitations to its questioning or queer potential. With every act of coming out, attention is drawn to the in-out, as well as the hetero-homo binary and thus to sexuality-related norms that LGBT activists criticise and that force many LGBT people to stay closeted (Morrish & Sauntson 2007: 98; Zimman 2009: 54).

Coming out has traditionally been viewed as the disclosing of one's non-heterosexual identification. The act of coming out is structured by regulatory frames that dictate what can(not) (easily) be publicly expressed (compare Butler's [1990] notion of "intelligibility"). These regulatory frames are not stable but historically and culturally specific and, therefore, changeable. Coming out as a gay man or as a lesbian woman has lost some of its stigma or sensation value in many Western societies due to a normalisation and increasing public recognition of these sexualities as legitimate. However, research demonstrates that the closet and coming out continue to be experiences that gay men and lesbian women regularly orient to in everyday interactions and that non-heterosexual identity constructions are still perceived as marked in comparison to heterosexual ones (e.g. Kitzinger 2005, Land & Kitzinger 2005, 2007).

Previous sociolinguistic and discourse analytic research has studied coming out from various perspectives, with most work concentrating on the coming-out narrative (Sauntson 2015) and its formal and functional make-up (e.g. Liang 1997, Morrish & Sauntson 2007: ch.2, Wong 2009). Other aspects covered by such research include coming out as a speech act (Chirrey 2003), coming-out advice literature, websites and training (Chirrey 2011, 2012, Didomenico 2015), and coming out in educational contexts (e.g. Ellwood 2006, Morrish & Sauntson 2007, Sauntson 2007).

More relevant to this study is work focusing on the discursive construction of coming out in the media. Morrish and Sauntson (2007: ch.6) studied outing practices to disparage politicians in the British press. The study draws on qualitative linguistic analyses to show how journalists use implicature, sexual innuendo lexis and camp talk to create the effects of a subtle pragmatic outing. Simultaneously, the focus of the study is the media-transmitted outing process itself rather than the linguistic shifts that a coming out evinces. In media and

communication studies, there has been recent work on the coming out of gay male sport celebrities (e.g. Kian, Anderson & Shipka 2015, King 2017, Magrath, Cleland & Anderson 2017), maybe because professional sports (especially male team sports) is a context in which traditional hegemonic masculinities are still highly valued and same-sex affection is viewed as a threat (see Nylund 2004). Research in the realm of pop music is less well represented (see Benozzo 2013). This may be because popular culture and the pop music industry have long been considered domains where more progressive explorations of gender and sexuality are common, accepted and even desired (Kian, Anderson & Shipka 2015: 621-622). However, as the delay of Ricky Martin's coming out shows, such a step, even in this realm, bears certain risks, especially in the potential loss of audience support.

The previous studies on celebrities' public coming out examine coming out texts and the ensuing media coverage. The present study differs from this earlier work in that it adopts a (corpus) linguistic approach and systematically contrasts the media coverage before and after the coming out to find evidence for discursive shifts. It is, therefore, not the act of coming out as such that is analysed here but the discursive consequences or the perlocutionary effects of a media-driven coming out (see Ward & Winstanley 2005).

Although recent empirical evidence suggests that the experiences of Latinx LGBT subjects in the US do not fundamentally differ from those of other LGBT populations (contrary to popular beliefs, they do not show lower rates of being out; Pastrana, Battle & Harris 2017), there are qualitative differences in the preferred discursive practices associated with coming out. While for white gay men in the US the explicit verbalisation of a gay identity tends to be perceived as a desirable goal, Latino gay men generally do not share this preference. This does not mean that the latter are less likely to be out to family and friends. But as their sexual identification is generally not explicitly talked about, it is rather

non-verbal means of communication (appearance-related aspects that clash with hegemonic masculinity or index gay masculinity, male-male co-habitation, etc.) that reveal a person's sexuality (Villicana, Delucio & Biernat 2016). This phenomenon of "tacitness" (Decena 2011), which is normally not viewed in terms of deception or being closeted by the verbally non-disclosing subjects themselves, has been described by a number of researchers in relation to various Latinx populations in the US (see, for example, Cashman 2018: ch.4, Decena 2011, Peña 2013: ch.6 on the experiences of Mexican, Dominican and Cuban LGBT subjects).

METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study uses the framework of critical discourse studies (Machin & Mayr 2012, Motschenbacher 2018a) and harnesses quantitative and qualitative forms of corpus-based linguistic analysis to uncover ideologies connected to sexual identity formation (see also Baker 2014, Mautner 2016, Motschenbacher 2018b). I analyse a corpus of news reports about Ricky Martin that consists of two sub-corpora: one containing texts dating from the time before Martin's public coming out, 1998 to March 29, 2010 (BEFORE); and another containing texts published after that date, up to January 15, 2018 (AFTER). While this temporal dividing line does not reflect the continual and reiterative nature of coming out throughout a person's life, it is here used to contrast the two time periods surrounding a celebrity's public coming out and thus the central moment in that person's coming out process.

The database LexisNexis was searched for English news publications with *Ricky Martin* in the headline to retrieve texts that focus on the artist. About 1,800 texts were retrieved, including articles from the printed press and news websites (interview

transcriptions were excluded). The data were inspected to filter out duplicate texts and texts that were not centrally about Ricky Martin. The final corpus consists of 1,004 texts and a total of 346,971 word tokens (BEFORE: 393 texts, 158,128 word tokens; AFTER: 611 texts, 188,843 word tokens). The majority of the texts originate from North American, Asian, Australian and European sources. There is a notable absence of texts from Africa (not a central target market) and Latin America (publications mainly in Spanish). In terms of newspaper categories, the majority of the texts are articles from nationally and internationally circulated broadsheet newspapers.

For a keyword analysis (Baker 2004, Gabrielatos 2018), two corpora should be compared that are similar overall but differ in one central aspect, which is the subject of investigation. This is achieved here by keeping the text genre (newspaper articles) and the topic (Ricky Martin) constant, as well as treating time period as the main factor causing variance. Comparative analysis of the two corpora yields evidence of the normative expectations of the (historical) context from which the data are taken, acknowledging that language use does not merely reflect social realities but also shapes them. Even though a wide range of topics and linguistic tools is potentially relevant for the discursive construction of a social actor, certain aspects may receive unusually high or low attention and can therefore be interpreted as motivated choices.

I used the corpus software AntConc (Anthony 2018) to compile two lists of keywords – forms that occur significantly more often in one of the two sub-corpora when compared to the other. This provides insights on the aboutness of the texts in the two sub-corpora. Table 2 in the Appendix presents word-forms whose keyness status can be claimed with a high level of confidence ($LL > 21.0$; for $LL = 15.13$, the error likelihood p is already below 0.0001). As the size of the two corpora is fairly small, statistical significance serves as a feasible entry

point into the data analysis (with larger corpora, many more significant findings would be detected, often based on relatively small differences; Gabrielatos 2018: 233-234). To provide information on effect size, Table 2 also specifies %DIFF values, which indicate the size of the differences.

An automated keyword analysis of untagged corpora has to rely on linguistic forms exclusively. A retrieval of the meanings of the forms, therefore, has to be part of the analysis (see Gabrielatos 2018: 226). The grouping of the keywords necessitated a familiarisation with Ricky Martin's biography. For example, all personal names listed in the keywords had to be researched and the relationship of their referents to Martin ascertained. Similarly, some keywords like *voice*, *sound* and *crime* were not relevant in their literal meanings but rather referred to various professional activities of the artist (his work on the TV show *The Voice*, his album *Sound Loaded*, and his appearance in the TV series *American Crime Story*). Concordance lines were inspected for many keyword items whose semantic classification was initially unclear.

The keywords were then grouped within semantic domains to facilitate data analysis and comparison. Semantic domains were established based on semantic similarities among keywords (basic semantic relations but also looser semantic connections such as between items belonging to the same conceptual field). The following semantic domains were used to classify the data: "ethnicity," "professional activity," "sexuality," "family," "personal reference," "emotionality" and "communicative verbs". For reasons of space, this analysis concentrates on two domains central to identity negotiation: "ethnicity" and "sexuality" (see Table 2). The domain "sexuality" is further subdivided into "sexual desire," "sexual identity," "coming out" and "romantic relationship."

Throughout the keyword analysis, semantic domains are illustrated with examples from the corpora. Finally, an in-depth analysis of lexical choices in two sample texts, one from each of the two corpora, complements the quantitative findings through a qualitative investigation of how various discourses surface linguistically in the data. It was decided to analyse two whole texts in detail rather than shorter passages from various texts in order to avoid cherry-picking effects. Shorter extracts may illustrate particular phenomena graphically but are less representative for longer text passages or the dataset as a whole.

KEYWORD ANALYSIS

Among the keywords in BEFORE, we find various word-forms that play a role in the discursive construction of an ethnic affiliation. Two of these keywords, *language* and *crossover*, are not tied to particular cultural backgrounds, but relate to ethnolinguistic identities and the mixing of ethnic influences. The other word-forms in this group can be attributed either to Latino culture or to white US American culture, thus bearing witness to the discursive construction of Martin as a figure who bridges these two cultures or introduces Latino culture to the US American mainstream (see also Calafell 2007: 88-97). Keyword items that refer to Latino culture are *Latin*, *Spanish*, *Telemundo* (Spanish-language TV channel), *San [Juan]* (capital of Puerto Rico), and *salsa*. Furthermore, we find numerous references to other Latino musical artists (*Gloria Estefan*, *[Jennifer] Lopez*, *[Marc] Anthony*, *[Rubi] Rosa*, *Santana*, *Julio Iglesias*). Keywords that index white US culture are *English*, *mainstream*, *America*, *U.S.*, and *Madonna*. The form *pop* may also be taken to index the white US American musical mainstream (in contrast to *salsa*). Among the keywords in AFTER,

ethnically relevant terms are restricted to two names associated with Latino culture (*Maluma, [Jorge] Ramos*).

The distribution of ethnically relevant keywords across the two corpora shows the higher relevance of ethnicity in the discursive construction of Ricky Martin before his coming out. This is illustrated by the following data extract from BEFORE, in which ethnicity-related keyword items are used to frame Martin's work as a fusion between Latino and white US cultures:

*The Ford ads will be broadcast in both **English** and **Spanish**, a testament to Martin's success as a **crossover** artist and his **mainstream** appeal.* [New York Post, 10.09.1999]

Within the semantic domain "sexuality", the sub-domain "sexual desire" is commonly represented in both keyword lists. However, there is an important qualitative difference. In BEFORE, we find relatively overt sexualised references to Martin's appearance in keywords denoting aspects of his body (*blond, hip, bon*, as in the song title *Shake your bon-bon*), or his attractiveness more generally (*appeal, Ken*) (see also Calafell 2007: 98). Furthermore, social actors qualifying as desiring subjects are only visible among the keywords in BEFORE. The forms *teen, girls* and *waving* indicate frenetic behaviour of young female fans as an expression of heterosexual desire:

*For them, the **hip**-shaking Latin **Ken** doll seems an overnight sensation but Martin has been speeding up the pulse of **girls** for years.* [The Gazette Montreal, 27.06.1999]

We can see in this example that references to the body (*hip*) and attractiveness (*Ken*) are coupled with references to female fans (*girls*), thus creating a heterosexual scenario.

However, this scenario is one-sided: the female audience is described as desiring Martin but not vice versa.

In AFTER, by contrast, the gaze is more strongly directed to Martin's outfits (*designer, fashion, Gabbana, matching*; absence of body-related keywords), and thus yields a less explicitly sexualising picture. We can, therefore, witness a development of desexualisation, from highly explicit heterosexual desire construction to a milder visual objectification. There is a notable absence of male forms used to refer to fan audiences in the keyword lists, which suggests that the importance of male fans has not significantly increased after Martin's coming out. Instead we see a decrease in references to the female audience segment. In contrast to the change in Martin's public sexual identification, there has not been a corresponding shift from heterosexual to same-sex desire in the media representation of Martin but merely a reduction in explicitly heterosexual constructions.

The centrality of Martin's sexual identity in AFTER is reflected by an over-lexicalisation in the field of sexual identity labels, which are absent from the keyword list of BEFORE (*gay, homosexual, sexuality, homosexuality, lesbian*; see Motschenbacher forthcoming for a qualitative analysis of the usage of such forms in the two corpora). Heterosexual identity labels (*heterosexual, straight*) are not key in either of the two corpora. This indicates that the importance of heterosexuality as an identity-related discourse has remained stable, whereas the topicalisation of non-heterosexual identities has substantially risen in AFTER. The fact that various word-forms of the lemma BE (*was, am, 'm*) are key in

AFTER also suggests a stronger presence of identity-related statements. We can conclude that the greater centrality of heterosexuality as a desire-related discourse in BEFORE (discussed above) is not paralleled by a concomitant centrality of heterosexuality as an identity discourse.

The lexically male form *man* is key in AFTER, indicating that references to masculinity play a greater role after Martin's coming out. This effect is supported by male keywords in other domains in AFTER (names of male partners and Martin's sons, the male nouns *father*, *dad*, *daddy*, *sons*, *boys*, *boyfriend*, and male third person pronouns). There are no lexically female nouns in the keyword list in AFTER apart from some female personal names within the domain "professional activity", while in BEFORE *girls* and the name of a female ex-partner of Martin are key. Viewed in total, this amounts to a shift from a more female-perspectivised, heterosexual construction of Martin as an object of desire to a stronger emphasis on the construction of masculinity from the artist's point of view (his role as a father, his male partners, his sons).

Other keywords in AFTER belong to the realm of sexual identity politics. We find the forms *LGBT* (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans), *GLAAD* (Gay and Lesbian Alliance Against Defamation), *community*, *homophobia*, and *equality*, which all denote or refer to aspects connected to discourses of empowerment:

*Ki-Moon thanked the star for joining the fight against **homophobia**, and called for equal rights for **gay** people [WENN Entertainment Newswire Service, 12.12.2012]*

Furthermore there is evidence for a higher degree of politicisation more generally speaking in AFTER, as the presidential names *Donald, Trump* and *Obama* are also among the keywords:

*Only days after his controversial declaration of support for same-sex marriage, President **Obama** was livin' la vida loca in Chelsea yesterday at a star-studded fundraiser hosted by singer Ricky Martin and attended by other prominent **gay** and **lesbian** donors.* [New York Post, 15.05.2012]

Not surprisingly, the semantic domain “coming out” occurs exclusively in the AFTER keyword list. We find three word-forms of the lemma COME (*coming, came, come*) and the form *out* listed. There are also other adjectives and adverbs apart from *out* that index the state of affairs after coming out (*openly, publicly, free*). Moreover, the AFTER keyword list contains various verbs and deverbal nouns that can be used to describe a coming out: (*revealed, announced, admitted, announcement*):

*The **out** and proud Puerto Rican superstar **admitted** he was in denial of his true sexual identity [...].* [International Business Times, 29.08.2013]

While constructions with *come out* are fairly neutral in how they represent the process of disclosing one's sexual identity, the other forms convey additional messages, as they describe Martin's coming out as sensational (*reveal, announce*) or as information that is

only reluctantly or shamefully given away, maybe because it is seen as negative (*admit*). Such forms also imply that the confessing person has hidden some information or even lied in the past (Chirrey 2003: 32).

Another set of keywords describes central aspects of the coming-out process, covering both the pre-coming-out (*struggling, realise, closet, decision*) and the post-coming-out stage (*reality, truth*). The forms *Ian* and *Thorpe* are coming-out related in the sense that they refer to another celebrity's coming out (see also Calafell 2007: 100-101 on the media strategy of associating other gay male celebrities such as George Michael with Ricky Martin).

Similarly to "sexual identity politics" and "coming out", the sub-domain "romantic relationships" occurs almost exclusively in the AFTER keyword list. The only keyword that belongs to this group in BEFORE (*Adriana*) refers to a former female partner of Martin. In AFTER, by contrast, names of Martin's male partners, and forms that are used to refer to their national origins or professions, are key (*Jwan, Yosef, Syrian, Lebanon, conceptual [painter]; Carlos, Gonzalez, Abella, economist*). Another group of keywords is formed by personal nouns denoting romantic partners more generally, in a gender-neutral (*partner*) or male fashion (*boyfriend, fiancé, fiancée*). Further relationship-related keywords in AFTER are *pair, relationship, dating, stability, together* and *split* (the keyness status of the preposition *with* also points towards a higher density of references to people in company with other people). The lexical items in this semantic domain overall suggest a discourse of relationship stability, as there is only one form (*split*) that explicates the breakdown of a romantic relationship. A final sub-group in this domain is marriage-related vocabulary (*engaged, engagement, marriage, marry, wedding, proposed*). The use of this semantic sub-domain is illustrated in the following extract:

*Ricky Martin has denied media reports that he is going to **marry his partner**, **economist Carlos Gonzalez Abella**, in a country other than his native Puerto Rico where gay **marriage** is not yet allowed. [Asian News International, 04.01.2012]*

As Martin married twice during the time period covered by AFTER, the absence of the nouns *husband* and *spouse* from the keyword list constitutes a marked gap that suggests that journalists are still reluctant to use these terms for married gay men. Due to the strong presence of other marriage-related vocabulary in AFTER, it is not the institution of marriage that is felt to be less compatible with gay couples, but rather the notion of gay men as officially married people.

An overview of the discursive focal points in BEFORE and AFTER as evident from the keyword analysis, including semantic domains not discussed in detail here, is presented in Table 1. All included domains are represented by several lexical items in the original keyword list. Besides the shifts outlined above, the discursive construction of Martin's persona in AFTER proves to be more family-centered, more personalised, more emotionalised and more communication-oriented. Within the domain "professional activity", more attention is paid to Martin's success and humanitarian work in BEFORE, while AFTER witnesses a broadening of professional activities from music to other fields such as acting, TV appearances, writing and social media.

[INSERT TABLE 1 HERE]

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS: ETHNICITY AND SEXUALITY IN TWO SAMPLE TEXTS

To take a closer look at how the discursive shifts identified at the quantitative level play out locally, I have selected two sample texts, one from BEFORE and one from AFTER (see Appendix), which focus on a topic covered by many of the texts in the dataset, namely Ricky Martin's tour performances. The commonness of this topic renders the selected texts representative for the data as a whole. Meanwhile, it was deemed preferable to select texts whose main topic is neither of the two aspects examined (ethnicity, sexuality), to show that the discourses uncovered have a broader relevance in the data. Sample Text 1 appeared on June 26, 1999 in the Canadian newspaper *The Globe and Mail*; sample text 2 on April 29, 2011 in the US newspaper *El Paso Times*. The analysis stands in the tradition of queer critical discourse analysis (Leap 2015, Thurlow 2016) and looks at lexical choices that are involved in the discursive construction of ethnicity and sexuality, showing how keywords work other terms from the same semantic domains to create identity-relevant effects and which more specific, sometimes competing, discourses are drawn on.

Text 1 (BEFORE) shows a strong presence of vocabulary that indexes ethnic identity negotiation, more specifically a juxtaposition of the white US American mainstream and Latino culture. Martin is described as occupying a leadership role, verbatim as *the leader of the Latin-crossover movement in the U.S. music industry* and as *the new King of Latin Music*. Besides the co-occurrence of English and Spanish personal names (e.g. *Ricky Martin, Rosie O'Donnell; Jose Menendez, Rebecca de Alba*) and the mentioning of English-Spanish song titles (*Livin' La Vida Loca, La Copa de la Vida (The Cup of Life)*), the article contains several references to language choice (*English debut, English language debut, bilingual, language,*

English, Spanish) and to the mixing of cultural influences (*Latin-crossover*). Paragraph 8 presents a discussion of language choice in the shape of a quote from the artist, in which Martin constructs the language issue as salient, especially in the *Latin press*, which he describes as taking a critical stance on the use of English in his songs.

The text also creates a connection between Martin's ethnic identity and desire, epitomised by the phrase *Latin Lover* (used three times), but also surfacing in other passages. In paragraph 5, for example, Martin's audience is described as *[going] to bed dreaming of Spanish and salsa and [waking] up crazy for Ricky*, and Martin's non-native English accent is eroticised (*his mildly accented English (just enough to be seductive)*). In paragraph 10, Martin is described as a *Latin lover* and likened to 1920s sex symbol *Valentino*. Furthermore, his Latino identity is constructed as being more desirable than comparable male US mainstream pop acts, as he is described as *hot spice in a sea of Backstreet-Boy bland*.

A competing discourse that sees Martin's ethnicity in less positive ways surfaces in Text 1 as well. It becomes evident, for example, at the end of the text, where a critical voice is adduced that finds fault with Martin's identity construction as being not authentically Latino. The aspects highlighted – *his whitewashed stage name, blonde-tipped hair and WASPy features* render his Latino-image compromised (or *watered down*, as it is said in the text) by the influences of the white US mainstream. This discourse also shines through in paragraph 4, where Martin's Latin lover persona is constructed as being inauthentic (*in heavy foundation makeup*), not fully-fledged (*he makes a subdued Latin lover*) and showing identity features that clash with the Latin lover image (*looking like the frat boy next door*). Other descriptions that are less compatible with this image include a reference to his face as a *Ken-doll visage*, which suggests a white, model-like handsomeness, and his dismissal *as the*

latest pretty-boy act, which indexes a young, maybe even feminine, type of beauty (both in paragraph 5).

Focusing on the discursive construction of sexuality in the text, it is obvious that sexuality is mainly conceptualised in terms of sexual desire. Martin is generally described as the object, rather than the subject, of desire. The text exhibits two major discursive strategies that contribute to this effect. The first type of representation centers around the construction of the fans' desire for Martin. This includes descriptions of the emotional effects that Martin has on his audience (*he blows their minds, to the delight of thousands of fans, hormonal flash*), and of how fans and media professionals express their desire for the artist (*women's vote for Latin Lover of 1999, the media ran to Martin like a teen to a ringing telephone*).

The social actors desiring Martin as fans are sketched out as female (*the women, the women and girls*; no male personal nouns are used), as having clearly sexual motivations (*mobs of randy females, "Chick porn, thy name is Ricky"*), as occurring in masses (*thousands of fans, more than a billion of television viewers in 187 countries, a crowd of celebrities*), and as showing wild or excessive behaviours (*the mob, thronging the streets of Toronto, continue to hunt him with bacchanalian fervor, camped outside overnight, gathered 24 hours early outside Sunrise Records*). This amounts to a fairly aggressive, unidirectional construction of heterosexual desire, with female fans desiring the male artist and a notable absence of desire expressions in the opposite direction. Even though a description as *Latin lover* would potentially allow for, or even suggest, sexual agency, Martin is generally not constructed as a sexual subject having desires or performing sexual acts on somebody. Still, he is not described in an asexual fashion, as the quality of sexiness is repeatedly assigned to him (*feeling sexy, his massive video sex appeal, charged with kinetic sexuality*).

Martin's own description of his fans and their behaviour in paragraph 5 is more neutral in the sense that he does not highlight the gender of his followers (*the audience*) and describes their reaction merely in terms of acceptance rather than wild enthusiasm (*I knew I would be accepted*). Moreover, he does not attribute his popularity to his physical appearance or ethnicity, but rather explains it with aspects that have informed the creation of his tour program (*great dancers, great band, a new concept of ... really getting to the audience*). This shows that the eroticisation of Martin's persona is substantially created by the media coverage rather than the artist himself.

The second discursive strategy is constituted by references to Martin's appearance, body and body movements, thus rendering the artist an object of the public gaze. That this is clearly an eroticising gaze becomes apparent when we consider which body parts and postures are highlighted. Most of them traditionally play a role in the erotic depiction of the human body (*tongue, chiselled features, his face falling back into marble-etched symmetry, visage, mug, pelvic thrust, gyrating pelvis, swivelled his slim hips, lounging*). However, they are not necessarily associated with the stereotypical eroticisation of the male body more specifically (see Motschenbacher 2009). One also finds references to physical attractiveness more generally that position Martin as the object of a stereotypically feminine gaze (*pretty-boy act, a "cutie patootie"*).

An identity-related sexuality discourse surfaces only minimally in Text 1, which dovetails with the fact that an overt sexual identification had not taken place at that time. Interestingly, paragraph 3 provides a quote by Martin in which he engages in sexuality-related definitional work: "*sensuality and sexuality are two different things. Sensuality is something you give to the world. Sexuality is something I keep for myself.*" In this description, Martin defines "sensuality" in terms of sexual desire, as something that he evokes in his

audience, while he views “sexuality” as a private matter. This distinction is blurred by another Martin quote in the last paragraph, in which the artist constructs his sexual identity as something that can be made a public object of desire: “*Showbiz is about fantasy. You want to fantasize I’m gay? Go ahead. People can fantasize about me whatever way they want.*” Sexual identity as a potentially hidden aspect is also co-constructed outside direct quotes in the text, surfacing in speculations whether Martin would be willing to *share his sexuality, whether he’s gay, or whether he is secretly married to sometime girlfriend Rebecca de Alba.*

In Sample Text 2 (AFTER), ethnic identity negotiation is clearly backgrounded. Besides references to Spanish and English song titles, there are only two ethnically relevant constructions, one reference to Martin as *the Puerto Rican hunk* (paragraph 1) and a description of his music as *pre-American crossover hits* (paragraph 9). Both of these phrases point to the singer’s life and career before he entered the US music market, so in contrast to Text 1, there are no explicit references to a fusion of white US and Latino cultures (even the song and album titles in Text 2 are not bilingual, but either English or Spanish).

As far as the discursive construction of sexuality is concerned, it is evident that desire and sexual identity constructions are equally prevalent in Text 2, whereas desire constructions clearly predominate in Text 1. The sexual identity discourse in Text 2 surfaces, for example, in references to *his sexuality, his homosexuality* and *his sexual orientation*, with the possessive constructions suggesting Martin’s own sexual identification rather than a media-driven identity negotiation as in Text 1. In connection with these phrases, the text also points to the public speculations about Martin’s sexuality that pre-dated his coming out (*speculation about his sexual orientation that dates back [...], rumors about his homosexuality have filled tabloids, he was too young to have his sexuality speculated about*).

References to coming out (*his decision to come out of the closet, Martin came out of the closet, his confessional new autobiography, setting yourself free*, the performance symbolism of *[breaking] the metal chains*) complement the picture of a self-determined sexual identification. Coming out is here constructed in a highly positive fashion, as *a monumental moment in his life and his career* or as a matter of *personal transformation*, and as supporting the politics of the LGBT rights movement (*liberation, empowerment, empowering, tolerance*).

A competing homophobic discourse can be identified, for example, in the uncritical use of the term *homosexuality*, which has pathological connotations. Homophobia is most explicit in paragraphs 8 and 9, where Martin's liberating and emancipatory messages are deemed to be in danger of being too excessive or even undesirable (*fortunately, Martin doesn't overdo the tolerance thing; unnecessary videos, including one about one of the male dancers coming out*).

The discursive construction of sexual desire in Text 2 overall operates with less explicitly sexualised images than in Text 1, thus epitomising the desexualisation suggested by the keyword data. The few more explicitly sexualised lexical choices (*kinky sex, lascivious, slithered over and under one another [...] in not too discreet way, he cavorted flirtatiously with one of his female dancers, salacious choreography, he fought off three bullwhip-snapping, scantily clad female dancers, couch orgy*) describe situations in which Martin interacts with dancers. In other words, they are used to construct staged performances of (largely heterosexual) desire rather than actual expressions of desire (such as between fans and artist).

The construction of the fans' desire for the artist in Text 2 also differs qualitatively from Text 1. Fan audiences are here exclusively referred to by means of lexically gender-neutral forms (*Coliseum; the crowd, mostly in its 20s, 30s and 40s; audience; late arriving crowds*), with only one such phrase making reference to a high number of fans (*the crowd of 4,000*). The fans' behaviour is either described in a comparatively tame fashion (*the crowd of 4,000 ate it up; the crowd [...] would have loved it; audience singalong*) or not at all.

Similarly, references to Martin's outer appearance focus less on the direct eroticisation of his body (there are merely references to his face: *irrepressible smile, infectious grin, stern mug*), or are performed with a twist. Martin is, for example, constructed *as the man with the thin, pleasant voice, irrepressible smile and rubbery hips* – a description in which the modifiers *thin, irrepressible* and *rubbery* carry fairly negative connotations and can thus hardly contribute to an eroticisation. Otherwise, references to physical attractiveness are in Text 2 restricted to the dancers in Martin's performance (*his four female and four male dancers – all very fit, all very good looking*). The description of Martin's appearance mainly focuses on his outfits (*the black leather-clad singer, he wore black leather and a sheer, hooded shirt (Armani outfitted the tour), black-and-white fashion scheme, white and light brown muscle shirts*).

To summarise, Text 2 does construct the public gaze on Martin, but this gaze is no longer explicitly heterosexual or female-perspectivised. In addition, the description is less focused on the sexual objectification of Martin's body, specifies less excessive desire expressions on the part of the fans, and restricts more explicitly sexualised wordings to the description of enacted desire as part of the stage performance.

CONCLUSION

This study has shed new light on the sociolinguistic discussion of coming out through a systematic quantitative and qualitative corpus-based analysis of the media coverage of a celebrity before and after his public coming out. More specifically, the data point to discursive shifts in the representation of ethnicity and sexuality.

The keyword analysis shows that the discursive construction of Martin's persona focused more on his ethnic and/or ethnolinguistic identity before his coming out. Sexuality has become the dominant identity feature after his coming out, thus yielding evidence for the subtractive relationship between the two identifications in the public eye: as soon as sexuality becomes a salient issue, ethnicity is backgrounded, even though it was the dominant identity-related discourse before. The keywords also suggest a tendency to construct Martin in a more sexually explicit, objectifying and heteronormative way in BEFORE. Not surprisingly, sexual identity politics and coming out have become central themes in the press coverage in AFTER. This shift coincides with a desexualisation of Martin's persona: desire becomes backgrounded, while more emphasis is placed on Martin's role as a partner in romantic relationships (and as a father of two sons).

The in-depth qualitative analysis of two newspaper articles from before and after Martin's coming out has further refined the picture. While identity negotiation revolves mainly around the fusion of the white US mainstream with Latino culture, the discursive construction of an eroticised Latin lover persona and the unidirectional expression of heterosexual desire from female fans to the artist in the earlier text, the later, post-coming-out text shows a backgrounding of ethnic affiliation and cultural contact, a foregrounding of sexual identity and its politicisation, a process of desexualisation in the discursive

construction of Martin's persona outside the context of stage performances, as well as homophobic discourses.

The data also document how news media contribute to the normalisation of coming out as a liberating and ultimately positive experience, even though it is associated with negative experiences for many LGBT people (see Benozzo, Pizzorno, Bell & Koro-Ljungberg 2015, Chirrey 2011: 289). As pointed out by Sauntson (2015), coming out has become normatively expected, while staying (verbally) in the closet is generally viewed as negative, dishonest and politically irresponsible. The news media sketch out same-sex attraction as an aspect that traditionally requires lying or hiding and whose disclosure is newsworthy or performed reluctantly. The case of Ricky Martin demonstrates that a coming out places various identity-related normativities on (out) gay men (for example, a stable family and relationship life, being active in sexual identity politics, desexualisation). These constitute strategies to make a traditionally non-normative sexual identification more easily acceptable for the wider public. The identity-related implications of coming out, therefore, come at a price, namely the submission under a new set of (homonormative) norms. Taking into account that gayness is often thought of as an identity stereotypically connected to white middle-class men, it is not surprising to find that Martin's ethnicity is pushed to the background, as it clashes with homonormative expectations (see also Kian, Anderson & Shipka [2015: 635] on a comparable effect after the coming out of a black basketball player). Similarly, other aspects like female fans' heterosexual desire for Martin or overt forms of sexualisation and physical objectification are backgrounded after Martin's coming out, because they clash to some extent with what society views as compatible with a gay male role model.

What the news coverage studied here ignores is that coming out is culturally specific (Liang 1997). The fact that an explicit verbalisation of one's gayness constitutes a marked practice for Latino men does not play any role in the discursive construction of Martin's coming out. Another silenced but relevant aspect is that for non-white non-heterosexual people, a public coming out means risking the social support from their ethnic communities. Viewed from this perspective, Martin's explicit publicisation of his gay identity must seem highly unusual and pushes him towards the white end of the ethnic identity continuum. Research on the media reception of gay male and lesbian figures (Gomillion & Giuliano 2011) suggests in general that openly same-sex identified celebrities may have a positive influence on the self-perception of LGBT individuals. However, this has not been studied in relation to more specific, ethnically based populations.

An aspect to be explored by future research is how the discursive construction of Ricky Martin's persona manifests itself in Spanish-language media. The present study was restricted to English-language data and may therefore only represent an out-group perspective on the coming out of a Latino gay man. Discourses prevalent in Spanish-language media may substantially differ from the ones verified in this study. In addition, further studies on the discursive construction of the coming out of other celebrities will improve our understanding which aspects are specific to Ricky Martin's case and which form more general patterns.

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Table 1: Semantic focal points as evident from keywords in BEFORE and AFTER

Foregrounded in BEFORE	Foregrounded in AFTER
ethnicity sexuality: sexual desire professional activity: music, success, humanitarian work	sexuality: coming out, sexual identity politics, romantic relationship family personalisation, emotionality, communication professional activity: music, acting, TV shows, writing, social media

APPENDIX

Table 2: Ethnicity- and sexuality-related keywords in BEFORE and AFTER (in comparison to each other; LL > 21.0; numbers in brackets are the effect sizes measured as %DIFF; forms in [] serve to explain or disambiguate word-forms)

Semantic domain	Key in BEFORE	Key in AFTER
ethnicity	<p><i>language</i> (242.5), <i>crossover</i> (226.6)</p> <p>Latino culture: <i>Latin</i> (125.2), <i>salsa</i> (782.1), <i>Spanish</i> (76.2), <i>San [Juan]</i> (186.4), <i>Telemundo</i> (4174.9), <i>Gloria</i> (533.3), <i>Estefan</i> (790.6), <i>[Jennifer] Lopez</i> (226.6), <i>[Marc] Anthony</i> (293.3), <i>[Robi] Rosa</i> (533.3), <i>Santana</i> (2156.2), <i>Julio</i> (850.0), <i>Iglesias</i> (331.8)</p> <p>White US culture: <i>English</i> (174.9), <i>pop</i> (75.2), <i>mainstream</i> (485.8), <i>America</i> (141.8), <i>U.[S.]</i> (119.8), <i>Madonna</i> (806.8)</p>	<p>Latino culture:</p> <p><i>Maluma</i> (3268.5), <i>[Jorge] Ramos</i> (615.9)</p>
sexuality: sexual desire	<p>body: <i>hip</i> (559.7), <i>bon</i> (as in <i>Shake your bon-bon</i>) (133.0), <i>appeal</i> (663.4), <i>blond</i> (3462.4), <i>Ken</i> (2037.4)</p> <p>desiring subjects: <i>teen</i> (329.3), <i>girls</i> (163.5), <i>waving</i> (3224.9)</p>	<p>fashion: <i>designer</i> (537.6), <i>fashion</i> (461.4), <i>Gabbana</i> (3100.0), <i>matching</i> (2931.7)</p>
sexuality: sexual identity politics		<p>sexual identity: <i>gay</i> (572.3), <i>homosexual</i> (3858.0), <i>sexuality</i> (288.5), <i>homosexuality</i> (1275.5), <i>lesbian</i> (2847.5), <i>man</i> (229.2), <i>was</i> (22.7), <i>am</i> (251.7), <i>'m</i> (58.7)</p> <p>sexual politics: <i>LGBT</i> (5963.3), <i>GLAAD</i> (6300.2), <i>community</i> (147.5),</p>

		<p><i>homophobia</i> (3268.5), <i>equality</i> (2005.3)</p> <p>politics: <i>Donald</i> (938.6), <i>Trump</i> (8068.6), <i>Obama</i> (1415.8)</p>
sexuality: coming out		<p><i>coming</i> (260.1), <i>came</i> (126.2), <i>come</i> (90.8)</p> <p>adverbs / adjectives: <i>out</i> (48.2), <i>openly</i> (1050.9), <i>publicly</i> (910.6), <i>free</i> (231.6)</p> <p>verbs / deverbial nouns: <i>revealed</i> (573.7), <i>announced</i> (215.8), <i>admitted</i> (725.3), <i>announcement</i> (590.5)</p> <p>coming out experiences: <i>reality</i> (573.7), <i>truth</i> (373.7), <i>decision</i> (334.0), <i>closet</i> (461.4), <i>struggling</i> (4615.9), <i>realise</i> (4279.1)</p> <p>other coming out: <i>Ian</i> (523.2), <i>Thorpe</i> (8995.0)</p>
sexuality: romantic relationship	partners: <i>Adriana [Biega]</i> (3224.9)	<p>partners: <i>Jwan</i> (27185.0), <i>Yosef</i> (19605.8), <i>Syrian</i> (8995.0), <i>Lebanon</i> (2679.0), <i>conceptual [painter]</i> (2931.6); <i>Carlos</i> (466.1), <i>Gonzalez</i> (552.6), <i>Abella</i> (5963.3), <i>economist</i> (2931.7)</p> <p>partner nouns: <i>boyfriend</i> (1146.4), <i>partner</i> (465.4), <i>fiancé</i> (3605.3), <i>fiance</i> (3605.3)</p> <p>relationship: <i>pair</i> (2258.0), <i>relationship</i> (349.1), <i>dating</i> (1794.8), <i>stability</i> (5626.5), <i>together</i> (185.2), <i>split</i> (657.9), <i>with</i> (23.6)</p>

		marriage: <i>engaged</i> (7142.3), <i>engagement</i> (1584.3), <i>marriage</i> (657.9), <i>marry</i> (549.6), <i>wedding</i> (433.3), <i>proposed</i> (2931.7)
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Sample Text 1: BEFORE (source: The Global and Mail, 26 June 1999)

[Headline:] He's so fine he blows their minds

[Paragraph 1:] Singing sensation Ricky Martin makes his first ever trip to Canada this weekend to the delight of thousands of fans thronging the streets of Toronto. With his hit single *Living on a Prayer*, he has won the women's vote for Latin Lover of 1999. But is he more than a hormonal flash in the pan?

[Paragraph 2:] Ricky Martin doesn't wake up feeling sexy every single day. "Sometimes I wake up feeling like, 'Ugh!' " the 27-year-old pop star groans, bunching up his chiselled features and poking out his tongue.

[Paragraph 3:] "But, really," he continues, his face falling back into marble-etched symmetry, "sensuality and sexuality are two different things. Sensuality is something you give to the world. Sexuality is something I keep for myself."

[Paragraph 4:] Dressed in casual beige, lounging in the Sony suite of the Four Seasons Hotel, Martin seems much smaller than his massive video sex appeal. Looking like the frat boy next door -- though in heavy foundation makeup -- he makes a subdued Latin lover. But would he share his sexuality for a price? Martin smiles big, jumps up and gives an involuntary pelvic thrust. "Sure, if you paid me, baby." Ricky, Ricky, where have you been all our lives? That's what more than a billion television viewers in 187 countries asked themselves after Martin swivelled his slim hips before a crowd of celebrities at this year's Grammy Awards. The televised show has already assumed its place in history as one of those moments *A Star Was Born*.

[Paragraph 5:] And perhaps rightly so. Martin's performance of *La Copa de la Vida* (The Cup of Life) was charged with kinetic sexuality -- sorry, sensuality -- like a thunderbolt. The viewing audience turned off the TV, went to bed dreaming of Spanish and salsa, and woke up crazy for Ricky. The media ran to Martin like a teen to a ringing telephone; his Ken-doll visage was splashed across the covers of *Time*, *People* and *Entertainment Weekly*. He was simultaneously hailed as the new King of Latin Music and dismissed as the latest disposable pretty-boy act. "I knew I had the tools to make it a hit -- great dancers, great band, a new concept of . . . really getting to the audience. I'd been hungry for it for months, and I knew I would be accepted," Martin says of his big night, in his mildly accented English (just enough to be seductive). "But a standing ovation from Sting and Madonna and Pavarotti? I was like, 'Oh God!' Who could expect that?" [...]

[Paragraph 6:] And by the time Rosie O'Donnell dubbed him a "cutie patootie" on her daytime talk show, Martin was no longer able to travel by car for the mobs of randy females. The women and girls continue to hunt him with bacchanalian fervor, chanting the chorus to his bilingual hit single *Livin' La Vida Loca*. Earlier this month, when Martin was scheduled to perform on NBC's Today show, thousands of fans camped outside overnight; police were forced to shut down traffic around the Rockefeller Center during taping. When Martin arrived in Toronto on Thursday for his only Canadian stop promoting his self-titled English language debut, the mob gathered 24 hours early outside Sunrise Records on Yonge Street, where Martin would be signing autographs on Friday afternoon. [...]

[Paragraph 7:] Though hailed as the leader of the Latin-crossover movement in the U.S. music industry, Martin had already sold 15-million records worldwide before he recorded his English debut. Far from being a case of rags to riches, this is just the cherry on top.

[Paragraph 8:] "For some people language is a big issue. For me it's not. I've already recorded in Portuguese, Italian and French. The Latin press didn't say anything about that -- no, they just get upset about the English."

[Paragraph 9:] After immediately topping the U.S. Billboard Charts, Martin made the hottest sales debut in Canada this year, selling 62,635 copies in its first week out. Things happened so fast, the tabloids didn't have time to confer: One minute they're saying he's gay, the next that he's secretly married to sometime girlfriend Rebecca de Alba. [...]

[Paragraph 10:] "Sometimes I choose to educate the ignorant and sometimes I choose to ignore," Martin comments. "Showbiz is about fantasy. You want to fantasize I'm gay? Go ahead. People can fantasize about me whatever way they want." And, of course, they do. "Chick porn, thy name is Ricky," proclaimed Cintra Wilson in a recent column for Salon, the online magazine. Yes, oh yes – but surely there's more to this than a made-up mug and a gyrating pelvis. Is Ricky reviving the iconography of the Latin lover, a Valentino for the 1990s? Critics such as Camille Paglia say no way, pointing out his whitewashed stage name, blonde-tipped hair and WASPy features. Watered down or not, though, Martin is hot spice in a sea of Backstreet-Boy bland. [...]

Sample Text 2: AFTER (source: El Paso Times, 29 April 2011)

[Headline:] Ricky Martin's liberation celebration rocks Coliseum

[Paragraph 1:] There's nothing subtle about the video that opens Ricky Martin's current "MAS" tour. It's a theatrical sequence, shot in black and white to underscore the symbolism, in which the Puerto Rican hunk breaks the metal chains with which he is bound.

[Paragraph 2:] It's an obvious reference to his decision to come out of the closet last year, after speculation about his sexual orientation that dates back farther than "*Livin' La Vida Loca*," the 1999 smash that made him a superstar the world over. Once the short video ended at Thursday's Coliseum show, his first here in nearly four years, Martin appeared from behind the screen standing in the middle of a three-level metal structure that resembled the set from "*Hollywood Squares*" (he, coincidentally, was in Paul Lynde's spot!), his forced vocal

no match for the amped up, pounded out aggression of "Sera Sera" from his new, empowerment-themed "Musica + Alma + Sexo" album.

[Paragraph 3:] With words like "liberation," lines like "don't be afraid of yourself" and stunts like the black leather-clad singer's plummet from the second level into the arms of his dancers, it was obvious that this show was about more than just music, hope and sex. It was about setting yourself free. The crowd of 4,000 ate it up.

[Paragraph 4:] The guy's been a favorite here as long as rumors about his homosexuality have filled tabloids, and he's been performing here since the Menudo days, when he was too young to have his sexuality speculated about.

[Paragraph 5:] Of course, the man with the thin, pleasant voice, irrepressible smile and rubbery hips could have sung about kinky sex and the crowd, mostly in its 20s, 30s and 40s, would have loved it.

[Paragraph 6:] In fact, he did turn a mash up of "I Am" and "I Don't Care" into a lascivious declaration of sexual freedom as Martin and his four female and four male dancers - all very fit, all very good looking - slithered over and under one another on a prop couch in not too discreet ways.

[Paragraph 7:] Martin came out of the closet only a year ago, so it makes sense that such a monumental moment in his life and career, as well as becoming a father nearly three years ago, would manifest itself in the upbeat, empowering themes of the "MAS" album, his confessional new autobiography "Me" and now this tour. This is his liberation celebration.

[Paragraph 8:] One doesn't expect depth from such a guarded guy. Fortunately, Martin doesn't overdo the tolerance thing in a highly choreographed but inventively conceived and executed show. It deftly touches on the major phases of his adult life and career (thank goodness he left that Menudo tripe out) without placing too much emphasis on any one of them.

[Paragraph 9:] Instead, it groups them into four five-song sections, which are connected by unnecessary videos, including one about one of the male dancers coming out and another about racial tolerance featuring his black guitarist and music director. The first segment, where he wore black leather and a sheer, hooded shirt (Armani outfitted the tour), explores themes of personal transformation, ending with one of his last pre-American crossover hits, and first audience singalong, "Vuelve."

[Paragraph 10:] The second part, with its black-and-white fashion scheme and '20s cabaret feel, is more about fun and enjoyment, with Martin's infectious grin replacing that stern mug from the first part. [...]

[Paragraph 11:] By the third segment, the "Hollywood Squares" set was all but forgotten as Martin, his two backup singers (who did a lot to flesh out his sometimes thin and choppy vocals) and members of his 10-piece band sat down, or at least slowed down, for a lovely version of "Maria" on which he cavorted flirtatiously with one of his female dancers, a sing-along version of "Tu Recuerdo" and a medley of older hits "Fuego" and "Te Extrano."

[Paragraph 12:] The laidback tone, accented by his white and light brown muscle shirts, abruptly changed with joyless new song "Frio," with its jagged dance beats and a salacious choreography on which he fought off three bullwhip-snapping, scantily clad female dancers. "I Am/I Don't Care" and its "Eyes Wide Open" couch orgy followed. [...]